

COMPOSITION OF CATTLE BREED

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7180636>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st October 2022

Accepted: 05th October 2022

Online: 10th October 2022

KEY WORDS

Breed, breed types, plant types, color, barra types, yellow color, yellow color, fruitfulness, productivity, nutrition.

ABSTRACT

In cattle breeding, the generation-to-generation characteristics of stable transmission to generations belonging to the same species and the structural structures of the cattle breed are discussed, and the formation of independent types in the climatic and pasture conditions of each region is studied.

A breed is a whole group of agricultural animals belonging to one species, having a common origin, enough to reproduce "within", having similar biological characteristics that are the basis for distinguishing one breed from another and are stably transmitted to generations. is called Karakol sheep meet the same requirements for breeds of agricultural animals, because they are numerous, have a common origin, productivity, a number of morpho-physiological signs are the same, stable genetic strength. At the same time, the diversity of animals belonging to the breed and the productivity of the Karakol are the distinguishing features of the Karakol breed. All this can be explained by genetic diversity, genetic polymorphism

within the breed, which has arisen for various reasons.

According to N.S. Giginayshvili, intra-breed genetic polymorphism can be explained as follows:

1. The desire of Karakollik to satisfy the needs formed under the influence of the consumer's nationality, social status and level of material provision. Karakolchi has always tried to make the Karakol skins produced by appropriate selection and mating methods to be of different colors. There is no doubt that the efforts in this direction led to genetic polymorphism. The variety of Karakol products and constantly enriching its assortment with promising varieties is one of the factors of ensuring the quality of Karakol farming, which is an important branch of the national economy.

2. Objective historical and ecological genealogies of the development of the Karakol breed related to human activity.

The Karakol breed was created and developed side by side with other breeds of sheep, and this situation led to interbreeding of these breeds, often unconsciously, sometimes consciously, in order to increase the number of sheep. This has caused the external structure and productivity characteristics of Karakol sheep to be reflected.

Climate and pasture conditions of each region, for example, Karakol desert and Nurota Togoldi semi-desert massifs, led to the formation of independent types of Karakol breed adapted to that region. In natural selection, only the animals that were best adapted to the living conditions survived, while man chose the animals that could bring the most profit for blackbuck skins.

N.S. Giginayshvili stated that "in Karakol sheep of the desert type, the height of the legs should be considered as a positive product of natural selection, because in order to consume the required amount of feed, it is necessary to quickly cover large distances across the pasture high legs work. At the same time, it is necessary to consider the economy of covering the surface of the lake with strong, long, thick flowers with flowers.

Thus, the interaction of the sheep organism with external environmental factors and artificial selection led to the emergence of various types of sheep within the Karakol breed. Genetic diversity is the result of many years of selective breeding.

Ye. V. Odintsova was the first to estimate the productivity of two groups of animals of different quality and geographically separated from each other within the

Karakol breed. This scientific hypothesis was further developed by I.N. Dyachkov, M.A. Koshevoy, K. Yelemosov.

According to I.N. Dyachkov, the Karakol breed of sheep has the following structure.

1. Breeding and production sheep groups.
2. Breed types and color groups
3. Productivity (barra) types
4. Ecological (regional) types
5. Plant types

N.S. Giginayshvili recommends relying on the following principles when developing the composition of the breed:

- a) The basis of one classification should be one symbol;
- b) That sign should form the core of an important biological characteristic and embody its economic value;
- c) The sum of the definitions and descriptions of the components should correspond to the ideas about the breed or sub-breed types.

Based on these principles, N.S. Giginayshvili expressed the composition of the breed as follows. "is a unit of types that are divided into small groups on the basis of smaller characteristic features and are connected to each other based on the similarity of the main features and characteristics, and are separated by different levels of content. In his opinion, ecological type cannot be recognized as a category of zootechnics, since it is not of great importance in the selection process.

N.S. Giginayshvili developed his procedure on the structural structure of the Karakol breed based on what was said.

According to it, the Karakol breed is divided into the following parts.

1. Breed types. The basis of this term is the color markings of lambs.
2. Plant types
3. The color is bright

4. Barra types

According to the scientist, groups of Karakol sheep that meet the following requirements can be considered a breed type:

- a) differs in the color of the main sign;
- b) the number of included goods is much larger;
- c) the transmission of color to generations is sufficiently stable;
- g) belongs to the organizational structure of the breed;
- d) has some internal polymorphism.

K. Yelemosov interprets the composition of the breed in a different way, according to which the composition of the breed is as follows:

1. Ecological geographical types
2. Breed types by color
3. Wool constitutional types
4. Productivity (barra) types
5. Plant types

In our opinion, one of the main factors determining the content of the breed is the animal's adaptation to certain conditions, the tolerance of its organism to environmental influences.

The fact that the breeding value of all groups of animals is not the same makes it necessary to consider the following categories in the structural structure of the Karakol breed:

- A group of animals engaged in breeding and production
- Breed types by color
- Productivity (barra) types
- Types of constitution
- Ecological (regional) types

1. Plant types

Breed types according to color imply dividing sheep into eight groups based on the color of the fiber coat at birth: black, blue, Bukhara suri, Surkhandaryasuri, Karakalpaksuri, Guligaz, Kambarvaak. Black

and blue serpusht Askania sheep are separated as an independent breed type.

Productivity (barra) types are divided into the following types: semi-circular flower (jacket), flat flower (flat), rib-shaped (rib-shaped), ovate-shaped (Caucasian) and black-flowered. In natural selection, only the animals that were best adapted to the living conditions survived, while man chose the animals that could bring the most profit for blackbuck skins.

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Breed and plant types of Karakol sheep

Inbreeding types	Plant types
Black color	In Uzbekistan: Karakum, Nishon, Mubarak, Pomiq, Konimex, Ulus; In Kazakhstan: Zadaryo, Tasti; In Turkmenistan: UchAji, Ravnina, Tejon; In Tajikistan: Qabadian.
Blue	In Uzbekistan: Southern Uzbekistan, Nurato, Guzor, Bobotog; In Kazakhstan: Gurevva Talas; In Tajikistan: Qabadian.
Sur color	In Uzbekistan: Sverdlov, Navoi, Karakum, Kyzylkum
Bukhara image	Nurato, In Turkmenistan: Tollimarjon
Suri of Surkhandarya	White blood
Karakalpak image	
White color	Gagarin white and Samarkand white marten
Light brown	Saikhan

The weight of different types of black sheep in the herds of Uzbekistan and other friendly countries is different, in general, among the sheep in the herds, the weight of black, blue and Bukhara sheep is 95% constitutes

The composition of the breed is constantly changing in general, especially by region: the ratio of breed types changes depending on the economic efficiency of the production of blacks in different color, coloration and barra groups based on market demands. The intrabreed and plant types existing in the Karakol breed were created by strengthening the positive changes of productivity in the heredity of animals in the selection process. The scope of the achievement of this process and the level of change in productivity is the need of the community, as well as the ability of the cattle breeder to notice changes in the productivity of herd animals in general, to breed animals with appropriate characteristics and to strengthen these positive changes in their heredity. depends. A certain group of Karakol sheep has a certain degree of independence within the boundaries of the breed.

A certain degree of independence of some groups of sheep within the Karakol breed creates a favorable environment for the development of the breed, gives enthusiasm to its development, the frequently changing pastures of deserts and semi-deserts - ensures rapid adaptation to nutritional conditions.

Interbreeding of inbred types, regional-ecological types, mutual exchange of rams of breeding plants with similar direction of productivity, increase of viability and prevention of inbreeding provides superiority of inbreeding.

The expansion of the distribution area of the representatives of the breed, their manifestation in different forms, the complexity of the structural structure creates a mixed scenic struggle in breeding work. However, targeted selection works in a certain direction leave no room for such a factor.

Focusing on the specified direction of work with the breed, the use of uniform selection and mating methods, centralized breeding of breeding animals according to the plan and providing farms with them ensure the integrity and viability of the breed.

The important task of the breeders is the rational use of the complex structure of this breed, which serves to satisfy the needs of consumers for the skins of the black type, color and variety. The correct solution to

these tasks would be to create a new type of sheep flock, to create a new type and color of black sheep, which would be needed both in the foreign and domestic fur markets.

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